

Approaching zero power: the role of the spontaneous fission in CROCUS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we investigate the impact of spontaneous fission when approaching zero power in uranium-fueled reactors, taking the CROCUS reactor as a case study. In the regime of very low power (i.e., in the milliwatt range), the contribution of neutrons produced by spontaneous fission from ^{238}U becomes non-negligible, and must be included in the neutron balance. Through a series of dedicated experiments, we assess the influence of spontaneous fission on the CROCUS stability conditions, focusing in particular on the water level required to ensure a stationary neutron flux. Below a given power threshold, the fission chains become sensitive to the extra neutrons added by spontaneous fission, and a steady state can be only sustained by inserting a negative reactivity. Furthermore, we characterize the effect of spontaneous fission on the axial neutron flux shape, by comparing the profiles obtained at various power regimes, combining experimental data from a three-dimensional detection array with theoretical predictions from a simple neutron diffusion model.

Keywords: Spontaneous fission, CROCUS, zero-power, sub-critical

1. INTRODUCTION

For the analysis of uranium-fueled nuclear reactors operating at extremely low power, the effect of neutrons originating from spontaneous fission of ^{238}U must be taken into account as an external source term. Indeed, spontaneous fission of ^{238}U emits approximately 1.36×10^{-2} neutrons per second per gram [1, 2], a non-negligible contribution when the fission rate in the core is very low. Other neutron emissions, such as those arising from (α, n) reactions on oxygen, or from spontaneous fission of ^{235}U , could also be considered; however, their contributions are negligible in practice, compared to that of the spontaneous fission of ^{238}U [3].

As part of an experimental campaign aimed at detecting and characterizing neutron clustering and spatial correlations, in this work we set out to characterize a stable operating regime at extremely low-power in the CROCUS reactor, in essence operating at sub-criticality with the spontaneous fission source. This study is motivated by recent theoretical [4] and experimental [3] activities that have shown that non-trivial neutron fluctuations might emerge in reactor cores operated at low-power conditions. In such a regime, where the neutron population remains sparse, assessing the impact of spontaneous fission on both the neutron balance and the spatial distribution of the flux is essential prior to the interpretation of spatial correlation measurements.

This paper is structured as follows: in Sec. 2 we discuss the impact of the spontaneous fission source in approaching the milliwatt power range, showing that reactor stability at very low power requires a

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negative reactivity insertion, due to the impact of the spontaneous fission source. Then, in Sec. 3 we examine the influence of spontaneous fission on the axial neutron flux shape using experimental measurements supported by a simple one-dimensional neutron diffusion model. Finally, the implications of the spontaneous fission contribution for reactor operation at low power will be analyzed in Sec. 4.

2. IMPACT OF THE SPONTANEOUS FISSION ON THE STABLE WATER LEVEL

CROCUS is a light-water-moderated reactor licensed to operate up to a maximum thermal power of 100 W. The core contains two types of fuel rods: the inner core region includes 336 uranium dioxide fuel rods enriched at 1.806 wt.%, and the outer core region includes a variable number of metallic uranium fuel rods enriched at 0.947 wt.%. The number of rods in the outer zone is adjusted depending on the specific experimental configuration, and it currently includes 180 rods for hosting the SAFFRON detection system [5]. In CROCUS, reactivity is primarily controlled by adjusting the water level in the vessel through a spillway system. The reactivity is regulated by changing the immersion level of the fuel rods, which modifies the moderating ratio of the core. The water level can be set with an accuracy of ± 0.1 mm, corresponding to a reactivity worth of approximately ± 0.4 pcm near criticality. Reactivity can also be controlled via two optional rods made of B_4C , positioned in symmetrical channels in the outer zone of the core, with an axial position accuracy of ± 0.5 mm, equivalent to a reactivity worth ± 0.2 pcm [6]. In this work, for reactivity regulation we will rely exclusively on the adjustment of the water level. CROCUS is equipped with four monitors: two boron-coated compensated ionization chambers (north and south), and two fission chambers (east and west) calibrated in power and acting as safety monitors, enabling real-time flux measurements and accurate reconstruction of the power history. The reactor is also equipped with a Pu-Be start-up neutron source, which was not used during the measurements and remained in its shield far from the core. For a review of the experimental activities conducted at the CROCUS reactor, see e.g. Ref. 7.

Under standard CROCUS operating conditions (i.e., within the power range 1 W \sim 80 W) and with constant water temperature, the water level required to maintain a stable neutron flux does not depend on reactor power. However, when trying to bring the reactor at extremely low power (i.e., in the mW range), maintaining the same water height as for higher-power operation leads to a positive drift in neutron flux rather than a stationary condition. In this regime, stability is restored by slightly lowering the water level, thus introducing a small negative reactivity. This behavior, familiar to anyone who has operated the reactor, has a straightforward theoretical explanation, which can be understood by examining the point-kinetics model

$$\frac{dn(t)}{dt} = \frac{\rho - \beta}{\Lambda} n(t) + \sum_j \lambda_j c_j(t) + q \quad (1a)$$

$$\frac{dc_j(t)}{dt} = \frac{\beta_j}{\Lambda} n(t) - \lambda_j c_j(t), \quad (1b)$$

where n is the neutron density, c_j is the precursor density for family j , $j = 1, \dots, D$ (with associated decay constant λ_j), β_j is the delayed neutron fraction for family j , Λ is the mean generation time, ρ is the reactivity introduced through the water level adjustment, and $q = \lambda_{SF} \bar{\nu}_{SF}$ is an external neutron source representing the spontaneous fission contributions, with λ_{SF} the spontaneous fission rate, and $\bar{\nu}_{SF}$ the average number of neutrons produced per spontaneous fission. Despite its apparent simplicity, this model provides a reasonable approximation for tightly-coupled systems like CROCUS [8]. When the spontaneous fission source intensity is negligible with respect to the average rate at which fission chains are created, the steady state is attained by setting the reactivity to $\rho = 0$ (in our case by adjusting the water level), which yields the corresponding critical condition $c_{cr} = n_{cr} \beta / (\Lambda \lambda)$. Under these assumptions, the criticality state does not depend on the power level, and can be sustained at arbitrary n_{cr} [8]. However, at low power the contribution resulting from the spontaneous fission source q cannot be neglected, which significantly affects the nature of the steady-state solutions of the point-kinetics model. In this

regime, the existence of a stationary solution n_∞ for the neutron density imposes a negative reactivity $\rho < 0$, which yields $n_\infty = -\Lambda q / \rho$. In this sub-critical regime, the equilibrium of the fission chains is maintained through the compensating effect of the intrinsic spontaneous fission source. Setting $\rho = 0$ when the source intensity is not negligible will result in a positive drift for the neutron density.

This result is coherent with the reactor behavior experimentally observed in CROCUS. In the 1 W \sim 80 W power range, the effect of the fission source is negligible, and the operation at the critical state does not depend on the power level. At lower power level, maintaining the same water height results in a drift in the neutron density, and the reactor can be made again stationary by decreasing the water level. The stable sub-critical regime depends on both the intensity of the external source, which is imposed by the amount of ^{238}U present in the core (which can not be adjusted), and on the level of negative reactivity inserted (which is adjusted e.g. by lowering the water level). Larger negative reactivity insertions yield lower power levels.

To confirm our findings and provide a thorough experimental validation, we performed a series of measurements in CROCUS, consisting of twelve different tests aimed at identifying the water level required to maintain the reactor in a stable condition across a power range from sub-milliwatt levels up to ~ 45 W. The objective is to determine under which conditions the spontaneous fission source significantly affects the critical state. In particular, we aimed at identifying two different operating regions: the regime where the steady state depends dominantly on the self-sustaining fission chains (with negligible help from the spontaneous fission source), and the regime where the stationary state crucially depends on the spontaneous fission source. The results of this analysis are illustrated in Fig. 1, where the water level of CROCUS corresponding to a stationary state is shown as a function of the power. For the sake of completeness, the corresponding numerical values are listed in Tab. I. The conversion from counts to power was performed using the calibration coefficients previously determined and reported in Ref. 9.

Figure 1 & Table I. Left: Stable reactor water level (left y-axis) as a function of power; the right y-axis indicates the reactivity associated with each water level. Error bars correspond to one standard error. Right: The power and the water level needed to achieve a stationary state.

Figure 1 shows that the water height required to maintain CROCUS in a steady state varies with power level and decreases sharply in the sub-milliwatt range. For the first five measurements, corresponding to powers between 0.3 mW and 2.5 mW, the stable water level is observed to increase progressively with power. Beyond this range, a plateau is reached: all subsequent seven measurements, from 11 mW up to 46 W, are insensitive to the water level, which is assessed to be 956.0 ± 0.1 mm.

The criterion used to establish reactor stability at a given water height required at least 10 minutes of operation without any visible power drift nor adjustment, verified and quantified in post-processing,

defined operationally as the absence of any clearly observable increasing or decreasing trend in the on-line fission-chamber count rates. In order to ensure consistency between measurements, precise control of the water temperature was imposed. Indeed, although CROCUS is a zero-power reactor, temperature variations are known to induce a reactivity feedback of ± 9.68 pcm/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$ [10]. This feedback can influence the determination of the stable water level among successive experimental measurements; therefore, particular care was taken to ensure that, for all twelve measurements, the water temperature remained stable at $20^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.1^{\circ}\text{C}$. All measurements were subsequently post-processed to identify and correct any drifts from a stationary state, for instance by detecting exponential trends and converting them into equivalent corrections in water height, assuming that near criticality 1 mm of water height variation corresponds to ± 4.15 pcm of reactivity [10]. For all the measurements presented here, particular care was taken to ensure that the selected water level corresponded to a stationary state of the core; this condition was imposed by verifying that any drift identified during post-processing required corrections at most within the accuracy of the water-level measurement (i.e., ± 0.1 mm).

The first five power levels were obtained following a consistent procedure during five different operation days. Starting from a critical state at approximately 150 mW, setting the water level deemed to be the critical one, the water height was lowered to the target value. After each adjustment, the reactor was allowed to reach a new steady state at the corresponding power, and stable operation was then recorded for a minimum of four hours to ensure sufficient counting statistics. The counts measured for these five power levels by the two fission chambers are shown in Fig. 2b. The duration of each measurement was chosen to achieve adequate statistics, with longer measurements at lower powers, while accounting for practical limits on the maximum feasible operation time. Lowering the water level for these first five states corresponds to introducing a negative reactivity insertion, whose magnitude can be estimated using the relation between reactivity and water level, which is approximately ± 4.15 pcm/mm near criticality [10]. Since the critical water level has been determined to be 956.0 mm, the amount of negative reactivity associated to each power can be estimated from the difference between this critical level and the reduced water height associated with that power. This analysis is illustrated in Fig. 2, which shows the inverse count rate recorded by the two fission chambers for the first five sub-critical states, as a function of the water level. A linear trend is observed for the sub-critical systems where the steady state is ensured by the presence of the spontaneous fission source. For each state, the corresponding estimated negative reactivity insertion is also indicated. For reference, the inverse count rate of one of the critical states, at 154 mW, is included as well. The introduced negative reactivity values are remarkably small, with the largest insertion reaching only -32 pcm when the water level is lowered by 7.7 mm, which confirms that the perturbation of the fission chains with respect to the critical state is rather small.

Our experimental findings demonstrate that, for powers below about 10 mW, stable reactor operation depends indeed on the contribution of the spontaneous fission source, which provides the neutrons necessary to maintain a stationary state. In this regime, CROCUS is in a slightly sub-critical configuration, where the equilibrium of the fission chains is preserved by the spontaneous fission source.

3. IMPACT OF THE SPONTANEOUS FISSION ON THE FLUX SHAPE

In the following, we extend our analysis of experimental data to the spatial shape of the neutron flux. For this purpose, we compare the measurements of the SAFFRON three-dimensional detection array [5] available in CROCUS to the findings of a simple neutron diffusion model. The objective is to determine whether, at very low power and under stationary conditions (i.e. when the contribution of the spontaneous fission source cannot be neglected, as demonstrated in Sec. 2), the flux shape is also appreciably affected. Experimental data obtained with SAFFRON consist of count rates acquired with a dwell time of 1 s by a collection of miniature scintillator detectors positioned at various inter-fuel-pin locations and several axial elevations: three standard layers (L_1 , L_2 , L_3) located at 15 cm, 50 cm, and 85 cm, and two additional layers which, by design, contain fewer detectors (LM_1 , LM_2) at 30 cm and 70 cm, respectively. This allows estimating the axial thermal neutron flux $\phi(z)$ along the z axis of the core.

Figure 2. Left: Inverse count rates as a function of the water level for the first five low-power configurations reported in Tab. I, where reactor stability is maintained under sub-critical conditions due to the contribution of the spontaneous fission source. The corresponding negative reactivity insertion is listed for each configuration. The critical case at $P = 154$ mW is shown for reference. Right: Count rates integrated over 100 s for the five sub-critical runs, as measured by the two fission chambers as a function of time. No operator intervention was required during stable acquisition.

In this sub-critical regime, using a single-speed diffusion approximation, the time-independent thermal neutron flux $\varphi(\mathbf{r})$ in the core obeys the equation

$$-D\nabla^2\varphi(\mathbf{r}) = (v\Sigma_f - \Sigma_a)\varphi(\mathbf{r}) + q_v, \quad (2)$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient, $v\Sigma_f$ is the product of the fission multiplicity times the fission cross section, Σ_a is the absorption cross section, and $q_v = \lambda_{\text{SF}}^v \bar{\nu}_{\text{SF}}$ is the (volumetric) spontaneous fission source [8]. Integrating Eq. (2) over the whole core, we have the global neutron balance

$$\frac{\mathcal{L} + A}{P} = 1 + \frac{Q}{P}, \quad (3)$$

where A is the total absorption rate, P is the total production rate, \mathcal{L} is the total leakage rate, and Q is the total spontaneous fission source. Using $k = P/(A + \mathcal{L})$, and $\rho = (k - 1)/k$, Eq. (3) yields an expression for the reactivity of the core in sub-critical conditions, namely, $\rho = -Q/P < 0$.

Following Ref. 3, we further introduce the approximation that the core can be represented as a one-dimensional system along the z (axial) axis, with leakage boundary conditions at the upper and lower core surfaces. This imposes $\varphi(z = \pm L) = 0$, where $2L$ is the total core height, corresponding to the fuel height covered by water, and the center of the core is taken at $z = 0$. Under these assumptions, and by further considering that the infinite multiplication factor $k_\infty = v\Sigma_f/\Sigma_a$ is greater than unity, the solution of Eq. (2) reads

$$\varphi(z) = \frac{q_v}{(k_\infty - 1)\Sigma_a} \left[\frac{\cos(z/\ell)}{\cos(L/\ell)} - 1 \right], \quad (4)$$

where $\ell = M\sqrt{1/(k_\infty - 1)}$ is a reduced length, and $M = \sqrt{D/\Sigma_a}$ the migration length. The maximum allowed value of the infinite multiplication factor is $k_\infty = 1 + M^2(\pi/2L)^2$, since the system is bound to be sub-critical due to the presence of an external source. The power integrated over the core is

$$P = \int_{-L}^L v\Sigma_f\varphi(z)dz = q_v \frac{k_\infty}{(k_\infty - 1)} [2\ell \tan L/\ell - 2L]. \quad (5)$$

For the sake of simplicity, we introduce $\rho_\infty = (k_\infty - 1)/k_\infty$, which is positive since $k_\infty > 1$. The volumetric spontaneous fission source integrated over the whole core is $Q = \int_{-L}^L q_v dz = 2Lq_v$. We therefore have

$$\rho = -\frac{Q}{P} = -\frac{\rho_\infty}{\frac{\ell}{L} \tan L/\ell - 1}. \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) relates the reactivity ρ for the sub-critical configurations to the migration length M and to the infinite multiplication factor k_∞ . The reactivity ρ is inferred based on the experimental values in Fig. 2. The migration length M is estimated using the Monte Carlo code TRIPOLI-4[®] [11], using the IFP algorithm to compute the adjoint-weighted value [12]. The obtained value of M is approximately independent of the water level, for the configurations examined here, and was estimated based on the critical CROCUS configuration described in the benchmark specification [6]. The infinite multiplication factor k_∞ can be thus inferred from Eq. (6), once ρ and M are determined. The knowledge of k_∞ allows finally reconstructing the axial flux profile according to Eq. 4. For the sake of completeness, we also estimated k_∞ using the formula $\rho = \rho_\infty \cdot P_{nl}$, where P_{nl} denotes the probability of non-leakage, which can be estimated using TRIPOLI-4[®]. Both approaches to determining k_∞ yielded consistent results, with only minor numerical differences.

We have then compared the spatial shape of the neutron density measured for the five lowest-power measurements (reported in Tab. I), as well as for the 154 mW case, to the spatial profiles stemming from the simple diffusion model. Results are displayed in Fig. 3. The configuration at 154 mW is taken as a reference, since at this power level spontaneous fission effects are deemed negligible and the water height corresponding to criticality is insensitive to core power (see Fig. 1). Despite the limited spatial resolution and the absence of calibration for absolute flux measurements, the SAFFRON array-like detection system enables direct comparison between measurements, allowing the five low-power spatial profiles to be compared with the reference measurement at 154 mW.

In the upper panels of each sub-plot of Fig. 3 we show the normalized axial flux shapes computed from the model in Eq. 4, for both the low-power cases and the reference configuration. The lower panels of the same figure display the ratio of the normalized (experiments and model) neutron densities to that at the reference power of 154 mW. Each experimental ratio is obtained by dividing, for a given axial level, the counts normalized to the total array counts between the low-power and reference configurations. Overall, the examined ratios show that deviations from the reference axial flux shape are minimal at all five power levels. Two main effects can be deduced from the displayed ratios. First, for a given power level, the ratio of neutron densities along the z axis has a decreasing trend, which mirrors the effect of the changing water level in the core. Indeed, at lower power, the stationary state is reached with a reduced water height (see Tab. I), leading to an earlier fall-off of the axial neutron flux compared to the reference configuration. Consequently, the deviation among flux shapes becomes more pronounced near the upper edge of the core, where the ratio exhibits a sharp drop coinciding with the water level of the low-power condition. Second, as the power increases and the differences in water height become progressively smaller, the deviation from the reference profile decreases, causing the ratio between the flux profiles to flatten toward unity.

For both observations, agreement between the diffusion model and the experimental trends is observed. Diffusion theory serves here as a qualitative reference only, since a rigorous quantitative assessment would require higher-fidelity modeling and falls beyond the scope of this work.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have investigated the operating conditions of the CROCUS reactor at low power. We have shown that in the mW power range the contribution of spontaneous fission is not negligible. In this power range, a stationary state can be achieved only under sub-critical conditions, with the neutron chains sustained by the contribution of the spontaneous fission source. The small negative reactivity

Figure 3. Axial profiles of the normalized (by the integral) neutron density for the first five cases reported in Tab. I, where stability is achieved under sub-critical conditions sustained by the spontaneous fission source. The top panel of each subplot compares each normalized axial flux, obtained from a one-dimensional diffusion model, with the corresponding profile of the 154 mW reference case. The bottom panel of each subplot shows the ratios between the two profiles. Theoretical predictions from the one-dimensional diffusion model are compared with experimental data from the SAFFRON detection system, discretized over five axial layers. Error bars on experimental results represent one standard error.

insertion required to ensure the stability of the power level is introduced by lowering the water height in the CROCUS core. Through a series of dedicated experiments, we have determined the stable water level for twelve distinct power states, showing that a unique level can be maintained across all powers only above a threshold of approximately 10 mW.

The impact of spontaneous fission on the axial neutron flux shape has been also examined using a simple one-dimensional one-speed diffusion model. Five low-power stationary flux profiles were compared to a reference case, and the trends predicted by the theoretical model were juxtaposed to the experimental measurements obtained with the SAFFRON detection system, capable of resolving the flux at different axial positions. The results confirm that deviations in the flux shapes are small, and predominantly reflect the effect of the water level, which must be reduced to maintain reactor stability at low power. The theoretical model employed in this work is intentionally simple and subject to inherent limitations. Future extensions of this study could therefore include three-dimensional and multigroup analyses to investigate spatially-resolved effects, such as the influence of fuel enrichment on the radial flux, as well as the impact of spectral differences between spontaneous and induced fissions.

Overall, our study contributes to a deeper understanding of the role of the spontaneous fission source in reactor kinetics at very low power, paving the way towards the upcoming experimental campaigns aimed at examining the behavior of spatial correlations of the neutron population in CROCUS.

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REFERENCES

- [1] D. Reilly, N. Ensslin, and H. Smith. "Passive Nondestructive Assay of Nuclear Materials." Technical Report NUREG/CR-5550, Los Alamos National Laboratory (1991).
- [2] N. O. S. Simakov, M. Verpelli. "Update of the nuclear data for the neutron emissions for actinides of interest in safeguards." *Nuclear Data Section, IAEA* (2015).
- [3] E. Dumonteil, R. Bahran, T. Cutler, et al. "Patchy nuclear chain reactions." *Communications Physics*, **volume 4** (2021).
- [4] A. Zoia and E. Dumonteil. "Neutron clustering: spatial fluctuations in multiplying systems at the critical point." In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Mathematics and Computational Methods Applied to Nuclear Science and Engineering (M&C 2017)*. Jeju, South Korea (2017).
- [5] F. Vitullo. *Miniature and Minimalistic Neutron Detectors for Online High-Resolution Experiments in the Zero-Power Reactor CROCUS*. Ph.D. dissertation, EPFL, Lausanne, Switzerland (2022).
- [6] OECD/NEA. "Benchmark on the kinetics parameters of the CROCUS reactor." Technical Report NEA 4440, OECD Nuclear Energy Agency (2007).
- [7] V. Lamirand. "Ten springs of experiments in CROCUS." *EPJ Web of Conferences*, **volume 288** (2023).
- [8] G. I. Bell and S. Glasstone. *Nuclear Reactor Theory*. Van Nostrand and Reinhold, NY, USA (1970).
- [9] V. Lamirand, A. Laureau, O. Pakari, P. Frajtag, and A. Pautz. "Power calibration methodology at the CROCUS reactor." *EPJ Web Conf*, **volume 225** (2020).
- [10] V. Lamirand, P. Frajtag, and A. Pautz. "Installation nucléaire CROCUS: Rapport de sécurité." Rapport interne N°17-48, EPFL, Switzerland (2017).
- [11] F.-X. Hugot, A. Jinaphanh, C. Jouanne, et al. "Overview of the TRIPOLI-4 Monte Carlo code, version 12." *EPJ - Nuclear Sciences & Technologies*, **volume 10** (2024).
- [12] G. Truchet et al. "Computing adjoint-weighted kinetics parameters in TRIPOLI-4 by the iterated fission probability method." *Ann Nucl Energy*, **volume 85**, pp. 17–26 (2015).